

Pyrazolone thiosemicarbazone based metal complexes: physico-chemical study, synthesis and biological activity

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Supplementary material

Conductometry data for Cu & Pd

[L]/[M] ratio	Molar conductance Λ_m -Cu				Molar conductance Λ_m -Pd			
	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C
0	13.440	17.978	23.03	27.327	5.9976	6.4876	9.0013	10.040
0.1	15.764	22.167	28.689	33.589	8.0311	10.059	12.142	13.381
0.2	18.118	25.004	34.221	39.734	10.510	12.328	14.499	16.052
0.3	19.829	27.645	38.592	46.706	12.117	13.827	16.375	18.678
0.4	21.968	30.164	42.889	52.92	13.210	14.935	17.796	20.300
0.5	23.629	33.305	47.544	59.633	14.082	15.611	18.722	21.251
0.6	25.547	37.249	52.283	66.934	14.513	16.057	19.423	21.971
0.7	28.240	40.635	56.497	72.324	14.881	16.424	19.889	22.353
0.8	30.768	42.546	61.054	80.458	14.974	16.743	20.099	22.515
0.9	32.804	45.623	65.758	85.407	15.101	16.944	20.222	22.809
1	34.426	48.363	68.698	87.808	15.170	17.203	20.384	22.976
1.1	33.659	47.735	71.099	88.2	15.185	17.257	20.320	22.887
1.2	32.833	47.686	71.687	87.759	15.082	17.292	20.305	22.951
1.3	31.830	47.280	71.295	86.779	15.131	17.316	20.349	22.912
1.4	31.417	47.182	71.295	85.995	15.180	17.297	20.423	23.020
1.5	31.535	47.04	71.246	85.358	15.229	17.262	20.339	23.083
1.6	30.798	46.648	71.393	83.986	15.253	17.350	20.374	23.142
1.7	30.355	45.790	71.491	83.202	15.366	17.360	20.393	23.206
1.8	30.060	45.682	71.246	82.957	15.425	17.380	20.310	23.284
1.9	29.972	46.280	71.099	83.006	15.464	17.409	20.212	23.328
2	29.795	45.790	70.658	83.594	15.537	17.365	20.241	23.196

Conductometry data for Co & Ni

[L]/[M] ratio	Molar conductance Λ_m -Co				Molar conductance Λ_m -Ni			
	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C
0	61.838	73.710	79.492	65.091	23.255	31.252	33.672	36.137
0.1	61.446	73.553	77.488	61.960	23.088	31.085	33.217	35.338
0.2	61.054	73.377	75.695	59.294	22.887	30.899	32.805	34.711
0.3	60.613	73.215	73.406	57.658	22.716	30.732	32.330	34.182
0.4	60.221	73.049	71.329	56.134	22.603	30.595	31.962	33.878
0.5	59.878	72.926	69.996	54.718	22.476	30.502	31.678	33.604
0.6	59.535	72.794	68.820	53.522	22.358	30.399	31.443	33.476
0.7	59.143	72.681	67.811	52.268	22.211	30.311	31.242	33.378
0.8	58.898	72.564	66.782	51.229	22.099	30.237	31.026	33.246
0.9	58.604	72.466	65.620	50.416	22.020	30.164	30.855	33.192
1	58.359	72.377	65.596	49.602	21.981	30.105	30.698	33.133
1.1	58.261	72.368	65.581	49.328	21.971	30.090	30.644	33.026
1.2	58.212	72.348	65.547	49.161	21.961	30.076	30.590	32.977
1.3	58.114	72.314	65.576	49.382	21.952	30.061	30.595	32.977
1.4	58.065	72.289	65.611	49.333	21.947	30.046	30.566	32.977
1.5	58.016	72.358	65.498	49.274	21.932	30.027	30.536	33.026
1.6	58.016	72.343	65.532	49.215	21.898	29.992	30.551	33.026
1.7	57.967	72.299	65.410	49.166	21.878	29.983	30.473	33.026
1.8	57.967	72.314	65.498	49.186	21.844	30.041	30.355	32.977
1.9	57.918	72.324	65.537	49.102	21.829	29.968	30.262	32.977
2	57.869	72.338	65.336	49.392	21.858	30.017	30.179	32.977

Conductometry data for Mn & Cr

[L]/[M] ratio	Molar conductance Λ_m -Mn				Molar conductance Λ_m -Cr			
	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C
0	72.652	85.313	89.998	83.378	68.712	91.203	100.99	68.688
0.1	71.829	84.338	87.053	81.281	68.379	90.380	99.416	65.390
0.2	71.177	83.525	84.186	79.590	67.771	89.704	97.769	62.661
0.3	70.662	82.878	82.442	78.022	67.267	88.876	96.417	60.534
0.4	70.030	82.280	81.276	76.812	66.865	88.278	95.138	58.691
0.5	69.379	81.687	80.511	75.724	66.483	87.485	93.761	57.496
0.6	68.977	81.080	79.639	74.798	66.164	86.862	92.796	56.452
0.7	68.516	80.658	79.095	74.092	65.939	86.328	91.713	55.100
0.8	68.178	80.369	78.943	73.328	65.728	85.960	91.267	54.007
0.9	67.904	79.982	78.547	72.730	65.615	85.754	90.801	53.498
1	67.673	79.708	78.292	72.103	65.498	85.588	90.439	52.542

1.1	67.517	79.600	78.184	71.976	65.459	85.534	90.434	52.317
1.2	67.404	79.384	78.120	71.804	65.429	85.588	90.302	52.023
1.3	67.424	79.355	78.066	71.887	65.356	85.534	89.998	51.846
1.4	67.399	79.252	78.052	71.486	65.326	85.529	89.944	51.685
1.5	67.365	79.090	77.846	71.427	65.302	85.534	89.998	51.797
1.6	67.384	78.885	77.787	71.603	65.312	85.500	90.008	51.753
1.7	67.340	78.782	77.723	71.657	65.233	85.505	89.959	51.714
1.8	67.286	78.728	77.669	71.388	65.214	85.470	90.003	51.611
1.9	67.193	78.723	77.635	70.795	65.184	85.485	89.988	51.101
2.0	67.139	78.762	77.625	70.359	65.160	85.509	90.003	51.028

Conductometry data for Hg & Pb

[L]/[M] ratio	Molar conductance Λ_m -Hg				Molar conductance Λ_m -Pb			
	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C
0	10.760	13.122	13.563	14.812	8.0605	9.9715	10.343	15.082
0.1	10.936	13.303	13.793	15.126	20.888	22.182	28.003	33.422
0.2	11.088	13.455	14.048	15.586	32.864	33.520	45.702	49.49
0.3	11.240	13.622	14.322	15.995	44.428	46.216	61.063	66.346
0.4	11.363	13.739	14.606	16.336	54.757	57.432	74.671	81.487
0.5	11.495	13.881	14.866	16.606	66.120	68.516	89.037	96.579
0.6	11.588	14.018	15.057	16.821	74.715	77.802	102.95	107.50
0.7	11.662	14.126	15.199	17.042	83.079	87.974	115.51	117.84
0.8	11.750	14.214	15.341	17.252	90.610	97.407	125.65	126.81
0.9	11.843	14.263	15.430	17.360	98.862	103.71	134.87	135.73
1.0	11.911	14.332	15.498	17.465	105.60	106.58	139.87	140.38
1.1	11.931	14.317	15.552	17.439	109.22	108.00	143.81	142.19
1.2	11.965	14.332	15.537	17.424	109.85	108.17	147.06	146.75
1.3	11.951	14.322	15.557	17.409	110.83	108.06	148.43	149.40
1.4	11.970	14.337	15.547	17.424	110.44	106.58	149.08	150.52
1.5	11.956	14.327	15.533	17.444	109.56	105.22	147.71	147.88
1.6	11.926	14.312	15.518	17.478	108.33	103.54	146.47	145.04
1.7	11.921	14.317	15.537	17.497	107.8	100.82	144.42	140.63
1.8	11.951	14.332	15.528	17.483	107.45	98.166	142.40	145.97
1.9	11.916	14.352	15.567	17.512	106.72	96.093	140.61	147.04
2.0	11.921	14.366	15.552	17.537	106.62	97.720	138.27	145.97

IR data for ligand (T-1) and their metal complexes (C-1 to C-8).

SAMPLE : T - 1

SAMPLE : C - 1

SAMPLE : C - 2

SAMPLE : C - 3

Mass spectral data for ligand (T-1) and their metal complexes(C-1 to C-8).

¹H NMR data for some selected ligand (T-1) and their metal complexes.

TG Analysis graph for metal complexes(C-1 to C-8).

